

IDENTIFICATION OF ELASTIC AND DAMPING PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES FROM VIBRATION TEST DATA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a method for identifying elastic and damping properties of composite laminates by using measured complex modal parameters. The analysis model is established based on a finite element model which considers the effect of transverse shear deformation and hysteretic damping. The reduced elastic constants and material loss factors are selected as the updated parameters. These parameters are identified by minimizing an error function containing the deviations of eigenvalues and responses between experiment and analysis. The present method allows 5 elastic constants and 3 damping factors to be determined simultaneously. Numerical examples show that the proposed method for determining composite material constants is very effective.

INTRODUCTION

Composites have been increasingly used in various industry fields such as aircraft, aerospace and automobiles, etc. The determination of material properties of composites is of importance for optimum design, quality control and damage detection. Traditionally, at least three separate static tests would be required in order to measure 4 elastic constants of uni-directional laminates. For properties such as shear moduli, static tests very often yield poor results. The dynamic response of a structure is closely related to material density, elastic constants, damping properties, and its geometry. Vibration tests offer the possibility of determining the material properties. Therefore, in recent years investigators have developed some methods of determining elastic constants by using vibration tests^[1-4]. Usually, an error function containing the deviations between test and analysis results was established based on the eigenvalue or/and eigenvector sensitivity analysis^[2-4]. Starting from a set of initial guessed values of selected parameters, these parameters are iteratively updated until the difference of modal parameters between numerical calculation and experiment is minimized. Since it is difficult to find out an explicit expression of eigenvalue and eigenvector sensitivity matrix with respect to composite material elastic constants, plate rigidities are selected as the updated parameters. Like this, the large additional errors would be introduced for angle-ply laminates due to the transformation from plate rigidities to elastic constants. In addition, since the transverse shear moduli are not sensitive as compared to other parameters, most methods are limited to identification of plane elastic properties.

The importance of material damping in the design process has increased in recent years as a means to control noise and vibration in high precision and high performance structures. However, only a few papers discuss the identification of damping properties. In Ref.[4] the damping behaviour was determined from free decaying vibration.

The objective of this research is to identify elastic and damping properties of composite laminates from vibration test data. The reduced elastic constants are selected as the updated parameters. The damping is considered as hysteretic. The present method allows 5 elastic constants and 3 damping loss factors to be determined simultaneously.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES

A FE model was developed in Ref.[5] based on the following displacement field

$$\mathbf{u} = -z\mathbf{w}_{,x} + \varphi_x f(z) \quad \mathbf{v} = -z\mathbf{w}_{,y} + \varphi_y f(z) \quad \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{w}(x,y) \quad (1)$$

where, $f(z) = z[1 - (4/3)(z/h)^2]$, u , v and w are the x -, y - and z -direction displacement, respectively. φ_x and φ_y are rotations. h is plate thickness. From Eq.(1), we have the following strain-displacement relationship:

$$\{\epsilon\} = [\mathbf{T}(z)]\{\epsilon_g\} \quad (2)$$

where, $\{\epsilon_g\} = [w_{,xx} \ w_{,yy} \ 2w_{,xy} \ \varphi_{x,x} \ \varphi_{y,y} \ (\varphi_{x,y} + \varphi_{y,x}) \ \varphi_x \ \varphi_y]^T$, is the generalized strain vector, and $\{\epsilon\} = \{\epsilon_x \ , \epsilon_y \ , \epsilon_{xy} \ , \epsilon_{xz} \ , \epsilon_{yz}\}$ is strain vector.

By using Eq.(2) and the constitutive relation Eq.(A1) in Appendix, the total strain energy is

$$\mathbf{U} = \int \{\epsilon_g\}^T [\mathbf{D}] \{\epsilon_g\} dx dy \quad (3)$$

where, the mean elasticity matrix of each element $[\mathbf{D}]$ is given by

$$[\mathbf{D}] = \sum_1^{N_k} \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} [\mathbf{T}(z)]^T [\mathbf{Q}] [\mathbf{T}(z)] dz \quad (4)$$

with, N_k is the number of laminae, h_{k-1} and h_k are the lower and upper co-ordinates of the k^{th} layer.

In the FE formulation, Each element has 4 nodes and each node has 5 degrees of freedom (w , $w_{,x}$, $w_{,y}$, φ_x , φ_y). The element is shown in Fig.1. The transverse displacement is interpolated by using an optimal interpolation function, whereas the two additional rotations are approximated by using the linear Lagrange interpolation function

$$\{\bar{\mathbf{w}}\} = [\bar{\mathbf{N}}] \{\bar{\delta}\} \quad (5)$$

where, $\{\bar{\mathbf{w}}\} = \{w \ \varphi_x \ \varphi_y\}^T$, $\{\bar{\delta}\} = \{\delta_1 \ \delta_2 \ \dots \ \delta_{12} \ \delta_{x1} \ \delta_{y1} \ \dots \ \delta_{x4} \ \delta_{y4}\}$ and $[\bar{\mathbf{N}}]$ is interpolation function matrix. The generalized strain vector may be expressed by nodal displacement

$$\{\epsilon_g\} = [B]\{\delta\} \quad (6)$$

Fig.1 Rectangular plate element

Therefore, element stiffness matrix is

$$[K]_e = \int [B]^T [D] [B] dx dy \quad (7)$$

The consistent mass matrix is used:

$$[M]_e = \rho \int [\bar{N}]^T [m] \bar{N} dx dy \quad (8)$$

where, $[m]$ is the mass density distribution matrix and ρ is mass density.

The element damping matrix is given

$$[C]_e = \int [B]^T [D_d] [B] dx dy \quad (9)$$

where, $[D_d] = [\beta][Q]$, and $[\beta] = \text{diag}(\beta_i)$. β_i ($i=1,5$) is the specific damping capacity.

For an orthotropic lamina, there are 6 independent elastic constants, 5 damping parameters and 1 mass density. In order to investigate the contribution of each elastic constant to stiffness matrix, we can divide the element stiffness matrix into linear combination of elastic constants. For convenience, the 6 elastic constants are denoted by α_i ($i=1-6$), and, $\alpha_1 = Q_{11}$, $\alpha_2 = Q_{22}$, $\alpha_3 = Q_{12} = Q_{21}$, $\alpha_4 = Q_{33}$, $\alpha_5 = Q_{44}$, $\alpha_6 = Q_{55}$. Therefore, the matrix $[Q]$ of Eq.(A2) in Appendix may be written as

$$[\bar{Q}] = \sum_1^{n=6} [\bar{Q}]_i \alpha_i \quad (10)$$

where, $[\bar{Q}]_k$ is obtained by setting $\alpha_k=1$ and other $\alpha_i=0$ in expression (A2). Substituting Eq.(10) into Eq.(A1) and Eq.(4), and integrating Eq.(7), the element stiffness matrix $[K]_{e_i}$ corresponding to α_i can be derived. Then subsystem stiffness matrix $[K]_i$ may be formed. Subsequently, the system stiffness matrix can be obtained in the following form

$$[K] = \sum_1^{n=6} [K]_i \alpha_i \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the damping matrix may be expressed as

$$[C] = \sum_1^{n=5} [C]_i \beta_i \quad (12)$$

Then, the characteristic equation of free vibration system is

$$([K] + j[C] - \lambda[M])\{y\} = 0 \quad (13)$$

IDENTIFICATION OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS

For a set of given initial values of the material parameters, the FE model (Eq.(13)) may be established. Then, the selected parameters are updated in such a way that the discrepancy of the structural response between calculation and experiment is as close as possible. Assume that the residual between analysis and experiment is

$$\{\Delta Z\} = \{Z_c\} - \{Z_a(p)\} \quad (14)$$

where $\{Z_c\}$ is measured vector, $\{Z_a(p)\}$ is corresponding calculated vector, $\{p\}$ is parameter vector to be updated. Define an objective function

$$J(p) = \{\Delta Z\}^T [W] \{\Delta Z\} + \{p\}^T [W_p] \{p\} \quad (15)$$

where $[W]$ and $[W_p]$ are weighting matrices. The minimization of Eq.(15) allows to determine the unknown design parameters $\{p\}$.

$\{Z_a(p)\}$ in Eq.(14) can be approximated by a Taylor's series in the vicinity of an initial estimate of parameter $\{p\}$

$$\{Z_a(p)\} = \{Z_a(p^r)\} + [\partial Z_a / \partial p] \{\Delta p\} \quad (16)$$

where $\{\Delta p\} = \{p^r\} - \{p^{(r-1)}\}$. Let

$$\{R\}^{(r-1)} = \{Z_c\} - \{Z_a(p^{(r-1)})\} \quad [G] = [\partial Z_a / \partial p] \quad (17)$$

The minimization (16) leads to the least squares solution for the correction parameters changes.

$$\{\Delta p\}^{(r)} = ([G]^T [G] + [W_p])^{-1} [G]^T \{R\}^{(r-1)} \quad (18)$$

The correction parameters and the system matrices are updated in each iteration step r.

$$\alpha_i^{(r)} = \alpha_i^{(r-1)} + \Delta \alpha_i^{(r)} \quad \beta_i^{(r)} = \beta_i^{(r-1)} + \Delta \beta_i^{(r)} \quad \gamma_i^{(r)} = \gamma_i^{(r-1)} + \Delta \gamma_i^{(r)} \quad (19)$$

$$[K] = [K]_a + \sum_i \alpha_i^{(r)} [K]_i \quad [C] = [C]_a + \sum_i \beta_i^{(r)} [C]_i \quad [M] = [M]_a + \sum_i \gamma_i^{(r)} [M]_i \quad (20)$$

In practical application, only limited DOFs and modes are measured. The FE model needs to be condensed to measured DOFs. Assume that condensed characteristic equation of system is

$$([\mathbf{K}]_{ac} + \sum_i \alpha_i [\mathbf{K}]_{ic} + j([\mathbf{C}]_{ac} + \sum_j \beta_j [\mathbf{C}]_{jc}) + \lambda_r([\mathbf{M}]_{ac} + \sum_k \gamma_k [\mathbf{M}]_{kc})\{y\}_r = 0 \quad (21)$$

Taking the first derivative of Eq.(21) with respect to parameters α_i , β_j and γ_k , premultiplying by $\{y\}_r^T$, and using mass-normalization condition, we have

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_r}{\partial \alpha_i} = \{y\}_r^T [\mathbf{K}]_i \{y\}_r, \quad \frac{\partial \lambda_r}{\partial \beta_j} = j \{y\}_r^T [\mathbf{C}]_j \{y\}_r, \quad \frac{\partial \lambda_r}{\partial \gamma_k} = -\{y\}_r^T [\mathbf{M}]_k \{y\}_r \lambda_r \quad (22)$$

Then, the complex eigenvalue sensitivity matrix is derived

$$[\mathbf{G}]_c = [\dots \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \alpha_i} \dots \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \beta_j} \dots \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial \gamma_k} \dots] \quad (23)$$

where, $\{\lambda\}$ is vector consisted of eigenvalues. The response sensitivity matrix is^[6]

$$[\mathbf{G}]_r = [\bar{\mathbf{K}}]_d^{-1} (\dots [\mathbf{K}]_{ic} \{y\}_m \dots j [\mathbf{D}]_{jc} \{y\}_m \dots \lambda_r [\mathbf{M}]_{kc} \{y\}_m \dots) \quad (24)$$

where, λ_r and $\{y\}_m$ are measured eigenvalue and mode shape respectively, and

$$[\bar{\mathbf{K}}]_d = -\lambda_r [\mathbf{M}]_{ac} + [\mathbf{K}]_{ac} + j [\mathbf{C}]_c \quad (25)$$

In Eq.(23) and Eq.(24), $[\mathbf{G}]_c$ are $[\mathbf{G}]_r$ are complex because the measured eigenvalues and mode shapes are complex. Dividing $[\mathbf{G}]_c$ and $[\mathbf{G}]_r$ into real part and imaginary part, the sensitivity matrix $[\mathbf{G}]$ may be obtained

$$[\mathbf{G}] = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Re}([\mathbf{G}]_c) \\ \text{Im}([\mathbf{G}]_c) \\ \text{Re}([\mathbf{G}]_r) \\ \text{Im}([\mathbf{G}]_r) \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Substituting expression (26) into Eq.(18), the correction parameters and the updated system matrices can be obtained from Eq.(19) and Eq.(20).

The condensed system and subsystem matrices in Eq.(21) can be derived in a similar way as in Ref.[6]:

$$[\mathbf{S}]_c = [\mathbf{T}]^T [\mathbf{S}] [\mathbf{T}] \quad (27)$$

where, $[\mathbf{S}]$ represents matrix $[\mathbf{K}]_a$, $[\mathbf{C}]_a$, $[\mathbf{M}]_a$, $[\mathbf{K}]_c$, $[\mathbf{C}]_c$ and $[\mathbf{M}]_c$. $[\mathbf{T}]$ is transformation matrix:

$$[\mathbf{T}] = \begin{bmatrix} [\mathbf{I}] \\ ([[\mathbf{K}]_{uu}] + j[\mathbf{C}]_{uu} + \lambda_r [\mathbf{M}]_{uu})^{-1} ([[\mathbf{K}]_{um}] + j[\mathbf{C}]_{um} + \lambda_r [\mathbf{M}]_{um}) \end{bmatrix}$$

with $[\mathbf{I}]$ is identity matrix, λ_r is test eigenvalue, and the partition of the system matrices with respect to index "m" for measured DOFs and index "u" for unmeasured DOFs.

Finally, the identified reduced elastic constants are transferred to engineering elastic constants of the material, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{12} &= Q_{12}/Q_{22}, & \nu_{21} &= Q_{12}/Q_{11}, & \mu &= 1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}, \\ E_1 &= Q_{11}/\mu, & E_2 &= Q_{22}/\mu, & G_{12} &= Q_{33}, & G_{13} &= Q_{44}, & G_{23} &= Q_{55}, \end{aligned}$$

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

To illustrate the present identification method, numerical simulation tests for different completely free rectangular plates are done. The geometry of the plates are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Geometry of the plates

	plate 1	plate 2	plate 3	plate 4
dimension(mm)	350x250x2	350x250x2	200x200x5	200x200x10
ply-angle	all [0]	cross-ply	all [0]	all [0]

The FE models are built by dividing the plate into 5x5 elements, then, their eigenfrequency and eigenvector are calculated by using the exact values of the material properties given in Table 2 (taking mass density as 1480kg/m³, damping factor $\beta_4=\beta_5=\beta_3$). Only the transverse displacements are taken as the measured mode shapes. The first 5 eigenfrequencies and modes are used for updating. The 80% of the exact reduced elastic constants and 50% of exact damping factors are taken as the initial values. Table 2 gives the identified results of elastic constants and damping factors for different plates.

Table 2 Exact and identified material properties

parameters	exact values	identified (plate 1)	identified (plate 2)	identified (plate 3)	identified (plate 4)
E ₁ (Gpa)	113.9	113.90	113.90	113.77	114.72
E ₂ (Gpa)	7.985	7.9848	7.9858	7.9851	7.9883
ν_{12}	0.288	0.2880	0.2880	0.2875	0.2900
G ₁₂ (Gpa)	3.137	3.1369	3.1370	3.1371	3.1376
G ₁₃ (Gpa)	2.852	2.8040	2.8230	2.8499	2.800
G ₂₃ (Gpa)	2.852	3.2242	2.9070	2.8370	2.8160
β_1 (%)	0.45	0.453	0.450	0.687	2.706
β_2 (%)	4.22	4.223	4.237	4.213	4.148
β_3 (%)	7.05	7.120	7.050	6.889	6.929

In order to study effects of different initial values errors on identified results, 70% of 6 reduced elastic constants for plate 1 and plate 2 and [70% 50% 70% 60% 50% 50%] for plate 3 are taken as the initial values. Table 3 presents the identified results. To consider the effect of random measurement errors at the same time, 8 random data sets are used to simulate the measured eigenfrequency and mode shape errors, and amplitudes of the errors are taken as 1%

and 5% respectively. The identified results are given in the last column of Table 3.

Table 3 Identified results with larger initial model errors and random measurement errors

parameters	with larger initial model errors			random errors
	plate 1	plate 2	plate 3	plate 1
E_1 (Gpa)	113.90	113.90	113.78	112.53
E_2 (Gpa)	7.9874	7.9882	7.9851	7.9633
ν_{12}	0.2878	0.2879	0.2875	0.2642
G_{12} (Gpa)	3.1376	3.1370	3.1370	3.1564
G_{13} (Gpa)	---	---	2.8593	---
G_{23} (Gpa)	26.677	---	2.8337	---
β_1 (%)	0.410	0.451	0.320	0.443
β_2 (%)	4.243	4.191	4.215	4.230
β_3 (%)	6.919	7.033	6.897	6.909

From Table 2 and Table 3 it can be observed that

1) For all cases, the relative errors of 3 identified plane elastic moduli are less than 1%. 2) With the increase of thickness-to-width ratio, the identified results of transverse shear moduli are improved. 3) the predicted results of damping properties are satisfactory. Their identification accuracy is related to the results of identified elastic constants. 4) For different ply-angles of layers, almost the same results can be obtained. 5) When the errors of the initial values are larger, and random errors exist, G_{13} and G_{23} may not converge, or identified error is very large for thin plates. For moderately thick plate 3, satisfactory results can be obtained even the initial values of 50% errors are given. This is because sensitivity of different parameters on vibration response is different.

By sensitivity analysis, it is found that Poisson's ratio and the transverse shear modulus are not sensitive compared with other parameters. However, their sensitivity may be tuned by changing the dimension of plate specimens or ply-angles. In order to get the satisfactory results, the designed plate specimen should present the contribution of different parameters to vibration response, and the larger values of sensitivity should be tuned in the range of lower modes since the measured errors of higher modes are relatively large. In addition, the designed plate specimen should avoid very close eigenvalues so that measured errors are decreased. In order to design a good plate specimen, it is necessary to make a priori estimation on the elastic parameter. A simple direct method of identifying physical parameters in Ref.[7] may be used for this purpose.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a method to determine elastic and damping properties of composite laminates by using measured complex eigenfrequencies and mode shapes. These parameters are identified by minimizing the error function containing the deviations of eigenvalues and responses between experiment and analysis. The identified results show that the elastic constants E_1 , E_2 and G_{12} can

be always satisfactorily estimated. Although Poisson's ratio and the transverse shear moduli are not sensitive compared with other parameters, their identification accuracy may be improved by designing a suitable plate specimen. The predicted results of damping properties are also acceptable.

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APPENDIX: CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

The stress-strain relation in coordinate direction for a layer is:

$$\begin{aligned} \{\sigma\} &= [Q]\{\epsilon\} \\ [Q] &= [R]^T[\bar{Q}][R] \end{aligned} \quad (A1)$$

where, [R] is transformation matrix by which the stresses and strains are transformed from the fibre orientation to the coordinated directions. For an orthotropic material, under the assumption that each layer possesses a plane of elastic symmetry parallel to the x-y plane, matrix [Q] is

$$[\bar{Q}] = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{33} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{55} \end{bmatrix} \quad (A2)$$

where Q_{ij} are the plane stress reduced elastic constants in the material axis of the layer. The relationships between Q_{ij} and engineering elastic constants are

$$Q_{11} = E_1 / \mu, \quad Q_{12} = \nu_{12} E_2 / \mu, \quad Q_{22} = E_2 / \mu, \quad Q_{33} = G_{12}, \quad Q_{44} = G_{13}, \quad Q_{55} = G_{23}, \quad \mu = 1 - \nu_{21}\nu_{12}$$